

Twitter Suspension and Its Lifting: A Fairy Tale on Freedom of Expression in Nigeria

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Abstract

Review Article

This paper titled “Twitter Suspension and Its Lifting: a Fairy Tale on Freedom of Expression in Nigeria”. Specifically examined how twitter suspension and lifting negate freedom of expression in Nigeria. Literatures were reviewed in line with the problematic. The paper is anchored on the descriptive research design, utilizing the instrumentality of secondary methods of data collection and the theory of state consequentialism as propounded by Jeremy Bentham (1789), John Stuart Mill (1861), and Henry Sidgwick (1907). The paper found that freedom of expression is substantially restricted in Nigeria. Hence, freedom of expression is a theoretical exercise as against the practical reality preached by the principle of freedom of expression in Nigeria. Therefore twitter suspension and its lifting has significantly hampered the dictates of freedom of expression in Nigeria. The paper recommends that the abuse of freedom of expression and other fundamental human rights by public officials should be strongly checkmated through vacation of office occupied.

Keywords: Internet, Censorship, Freedom, Expression, Freedom of expression, Twitter.

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INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, the freedom of expression is protected by section 39 (1) of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Constitution 1999 as amended. Despite this constitutional protection, freedoms of expression have been controlled by the government throughout its history, even till date. Freedom of expression includes the right to express your views aloud (for example through public protest and demonstrations) or through: published articles, books or leaflets; television or radio broadcasting; works of art; and the internet and social media. Freedom of expression is a fundamental human right, enshrined in Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. They sometimes impose high taxes on newsprint, making newspapers so expensive that people can't afford to buy them. Independent radio and TV stations are forced off air if they criticize government policy. Recently the censors have come hard on cyberspace, restricting the use of the internet and new media (Nwabughio, 2021).

Internet accessibility reflects, inter alia, the willingness of governments to allow or encourage their populations to log into cyberspace. Repressive government often fears the emancipatory potential of the internet, which allows individuals to circumvent tightly controlled media. There are multiple motivations for Internet censorship, and thus

several forms and types, including political repression of dissidents, human rights activists, or comments insulting to the state (e.g., in China Iran, Burma/Myanmar); religious controls to inhibit the dissemination of ideas deemed heretical or sacrilegious (as found in many Arab states); protections of intellectual property, including restrictions on illegally downloaded movies and music; or cultural restrictions that exist as part of the oppression of ethnic minorities (e.g., refusal to allow government websites in certain languages) or sexual minorities (i.e., gays and lesbians). Typically, governments that seek to impose censorship do so using the excuse of protecting public morality from ostensible sins such as pornography or gambling, although more recently combating terrorism has emerged as a favorite rationale. Deliberately vague notions of national security and social stability are typically invoked as well.

The current Nigerian government has long held concerns over the use of Twitter in the country (TRT World, 2021). The End SARS protest began on Twitter and got amplified in 2020 when it had 48 million tweets in ten days. The government floated the idea of social media regulation on different occasions prior to banning Twitter (Kazeem, 2021). Attempts to pass anti-social media bill in the past have failed majorly due to massive outcry on Twitter (Omilana, 2021). Days before the ban, the then minister of information called Twitter's activities in

Nigeria suspicious, citing its influence on the End SARS protests (Channels tv, 2021).

This Paper adopts the descriptive research design, which according to Biereenu-Nnabugwu (2021) is regarded as critical and radical approach to current and past event of interest. He added that a study is considered critical in nature if (a) it is a social critique that exposes harmful or alienating social conditions (b) its purpose targets to emancipate members of the society from the harmful conditions, thus eliminating the cause of the alienation.

Consequently, the research essentially relies on documentary technique of data collection through secondary materials such as books, journals, magazines, newspapers, official publications etc, and employing content analysis as its method of data analysis.

Theoretical Framework

State Consequentialism, also known as Mohist consequentialism, is an ethical theory that judges and evaluates the moral worth of an action based on its contribution to the overall welfare of a state or society. The theory, rooted in the ancient Chinese thought, prioritizes the promotion of public good, including order, wealth, and population growth, over the preferences of the ruling elites cum bourgeoisie class of the society, without undermining whose horse is gouge. The classical proponents of State consequentialism theory are Jeremy Bentham (1789), John Stuart Mill (1861), and Henry Sidgwick (1907). A class of normative and ethical theorists who argued that the consequences of one's conduct are the ultimate basis for judgment about the rightness or wrongness of that conduct

Jeremy Bentham (1789), John Stuart Mill (1861), and Henry Sidgwick (1907) added that right and wrong are determined by what benefits all the people of the world, not by what benefits the state. The Mohists' concern is to benefit all people, considered as an aggregate or a community, not to benefit a particular political entity, such as the state or her president.

Hence it is the business of the benevolent man to seek to promote what is beneficial to the state and to eliminate what is harmful and not by forcefully means of imposition of sanction, ban or stoppage of what she felt that threatens the state. Therefore, what benefits the masses they will carry out, go for and retain; what does not benefit men they will leave alone. State consequentialism, also known as Mohist consequentialism, is an ethical theory that evaluates the moral worth of an action based on how much it contributes to the welfare of the masses within the state.

The Mohists believed that morality is based on "promoting the benefit of all under heaven and eliminating harm to all under heaven." In contrast to Jeremy Bentham's views, state consequentialism is not utilitarian because it is not hedonistic or individualistic. The importance of outcomes that are good for the community outweigh the importance of individual pleasure and pain.

Thus, the state consequentialism holds that decisions ought to be made in consideration of the best interest of the majority within the state. The theory further posits that any act consists in its tendency to produce things of intrinsic value to the majority of the state populace. Consequentialists hold in general that an act is right if and only if the act will produce, probably produce, or is intended to produce, a greater balance of good over evil for the populace than any available alternative of self-planned and enrichment ban stratagem.

History of Freedom of Expression in Nigeria

Freedom of expression is one of the major universal human rights which is clearly recognized and adopted by the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights at its 65th ordinary session Held from 21 October to 10 November 2019 in Banjul, the Gambia. And as a member nation, Nigeria is signatory to the African Commission on Human Rights Charter. According to the Charter in Principle 1:

- (i) Freedom of expression and access to information is fundamental rights protected under the African Charter and other international human rights laws and standards. The respect, protection and fulfilment of these rights is crucial and indispensable for the free development of the human person, the creation and nurturing of democratic societies and for enabling the exercise of other rights;
- (ii) States Parties to the African Charter (States) shall create an enabling environment for the exercise of freedom of expression and access to information, including by ensuring protection against acts or omissions of non-State actors that curtail the enjoyment of freedom of expression and access to information (African Commission on Human and People's Rights, 2019).

Furthermore, the Charter in Principle 2 stated that:

- (i) Freedom of opinion, including the right to form and change all forms of opinion at any time and for whatever reason, is a fundamental and inalienable human right indispensable for the exercise of freedom of expression. States shall not interfere with anyone's freedom of opinion (African Commission on Human and People's Rights, 2019).

In order to make the protection of the stated right of expression, the African Charter inserted Principle 10 a proviso that is tended to prevent member states from arbitrarily clamping down on individuals or groups who seem to possess and express opinions which are contrary to official views held by the government. According to the Principle:

- (i) Freedom of expression, including the right to seek, receive and impart information and ideas, either orally, in writing or in print, in the form of art or through any other form of communication or medium, including across frontiers, is a fundamental and inalienable human right and an indispensable component of democracy opinion (African Commission on Human and People's Rights, 2019).

More so, to ensure that states do not under the guise of prohibiting speeches that advocates for national, racial, religious or other forms of discriminatory hatred which constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence to impose a blanket restriction on the right of expression; the Charter in Principle 23 no. 3 declared that States shall not prohibit speech that merely lacks civility or which offends or disturbs (African Commission on Human and People's Rights, 2019).

In chapter 4, section 39 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, provision and guarantee for Right to Freedom of Expression and the Press were made. In subsection 1, the constitution provided that "every person shall be entitled to freedom of expression, including freedom to hold opinions and to receive and impart ideas and information without interference" (FRN, 1999). In the light of the fore goings, the ideal thing is that freedom of expression in Nigeria would be unfettered and unhindered.

One of the ideals that define a democratic system is the functionality of the rule of law. Freedom of speech, access to information, are both fundamental human rights protected by Nigeria's 1999 constitution in sections 22 and 39, Laws the Nigerian government constantly ignores as seen through its history.

Nigeria's Laws against Freedom of Expression

Since the '90s, there has been political intolerance towards the media, social media as government officials have been known to jail its critics, fire employees who do not promote or approve of their views and ideas as well as the subjection of the media to scare tactics and intimidation, through threats of possible imprisonment.

Republican Constitution of 1963

The section 25, a re-enactment of section 24 of the independence Constitution of 1960 states that every person shall be entitled to freedom of expression, including the freedom to hold opinions and to receive and impart ideas and information without interference. However, sub-section 2 of section 25 dis-abuses the absoluteness of the law. The subsection states that nothing in section 25 invalidates any law that is "reasonably justifiable in a democratic society in the interest of public order, public safety, public morality or public health". The clause allowed for the restrictions to the freedom of expression and would go on to birth more restrictive laws in the history of Nigeria.

Decree No. 4 Of 1984

Considered the most dreadful law against the media, Decree No. 4 was promulgated on March 29, 1984, during the military regime of Major General Muhammadu Buhari. The law was drafted to arrest and punish journalists and writers that exposed the Buhari administration or ridiculed officials of the administration. Section 1, sub-sections (i), (ii) and (iii) of the law – the most formidable section – provided that:

- i. Any person who publishes in any form, whether written or otherwise, any message, rumour, report or statement, being a message, rumour, statement or report which is false in any material particular or which brings or is calculated to bring the Federal Military Government or the Government of a state or public officer to ridicule or disrepute, shall be guilty of an offence under this Decree.
- ii. Any station for wireless telegraphy which conveys or transmits any sound or visual message, rumour, report or statement, being a message, rumour, report or statement which is false in any material particular or which brings or is calculated to bring the Federal Government or the Government of a state or a public officer to ridicule or disrepute, shall be guilty of an offence under this Decree.
- iii. It shall be an offence under this Decree for a newspaper or wireless telegraphy station in Nigeria to publish or transmit any message, rumour, report or statement which is false in any material particular stating that any public officer has in any manner been engaged in corrupt practices or has in any manner corruptly enriched himself or any other person (Gazette, 1984).

The law also gave absolute power to the Head of State to ban a newspaper and revoke the license of any wireless telegraph station in any part of the federation, if the action was determined to be in the interest of the nation. Two Guardian reporters, Tunde Thompson and NdukaIabor were among the victims of Decree No. 4 (Nwogu, 2021).

Decree No. 2 of 1984

Decree No. 2 of 1984 promulgated during the Buhari regime, this law allowed the detention and incommunicado of any Nigerian citizen for up to three months without charge. It gave broad authority to the National Security Organization (NSO) while outlawing every form of civil protest and worker's strike. According to Amnesty International, about 150 people, including renowned journalist and teacher, Tai Solarin, were reported to have been detained under Decree No. 2 in 1984. Former Biafran leader, ChukuemekaOjukwu, was among those detained under the decree. He was later released without charges. Musician and popular critic of the Buhari regime, FelaKuti was arrested in September 1984 and accused of attempting to unlawfully export foreign currency. He was handed a five-year jail sentence by a military tribunal. Amnesty International reported allegations that important defence witnesses, including customs officials, were prevented from testifying at Fela's trial.

Cyber Crime Act of 2015

In 2015, the Cybercrime law that allowed the president a level of legal control over social media expressions was enacted, President Buhari's rejection of the bill, referring to it as being "inconsistent with democratic ideals of free speech enshrined in the constitution of the land". This law was used to abduct arrest and detain 5 known bloggers in Nigeria. Under the

guise of Section 24 of the act which carries a fine of up to 7 million naira (USD 22,000) and a maximum three-year jail term, Musa BabaleAz was detained in Abuja in August 2015 for allegedly criticizing the state governor, Muhammad Abdullah Abubakar on Twitter and Facebook. Azare was denied access to his lawyer and was taken 450km from Abuja to a police station in Bauchi state to have his statement taken.

Hate Speech and Protection from Internet Falsehood and Manipulation Bills of 2019

Though never passed to law, these bills would be considered the deadliest bills against freedom of speech and expression in today’s Nigeria. One would have thought that the President’s virtuous words on the ideals of democracy and the rule of law would be upheld, but surprisingly, the 2019 Hate Speech and Protection from Internet Falsehood and Manipulation Bills were championed by the government. The bills aimed at giving authorities arbitrary powers to shut down the internet, limit access to social media, and make criticizing the government punishable by imprisonment or death. The bill proscribed a death sentence for people found guilty of “hate speech”. Vice President of Nigeria, Prof. Yemi Osinbajo said that the Federal Government of Nigeria planned to classify hate speech as a form of Terrorism, and offenders would be charged under the Terrorism Prevention Act, as amended. This brought about the debate of whether the classification of hate speech as an act of terrorism infringes on the right to free speech and whether its criminalization was not an outright infringement of freedom of expression as provided in the law.

Twitter Suspension a Move to Regulate Social Media

This government’s whimsical decision to suspend Twitter is unfortunately not backed by any legal mandate of our present constitution. For a fact, the decision goes against both our constitution and international law which provides that any restriction to

rights online must be provided in law, according to a legitimate aim, and limited to only what is necessary and proportionate. The Declaration of Principles on Freedom of Expression in Africa also provides that any restriction to freedom of expression must “serve a legitimate purpose, necessary in a democratic society.” One cannot determine the legitimate purpose of shutting down a network that is vital for social justice aside from the idea that the present government has zero-tolerance for anyone/ organization/ media that threaten to expose its uncanny knack of violating the legal rights of its citizen. It is on the above that Jacob, (2021) posited that it is a harrowing reminder of a similar historic regime of 37 years ago. Not only did the government suspend twitter, but the federal government has also ordered all social media platforms operating in Nigeria must be licensed by the Nigerian Broadcasting Corporation (NBC). Other social media platforms used by Nigerians include Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, amongst others.

Freedom of Expression and Arrests of Citizens

From April 4 - 11 2018, Paradigm Initiative hosted a poll 27 on its Twitter handle asking the simple question, “Do you feel free to express yourself on social media in Nigeria?” There were 2,294 respondents, with 47% responding “Yes”, 40% “No” and 13% responding “I don’t know”. Although the population sample was not random, the relatively large proportion of respondents who said they don’t feel free to express themselves (40%) is perhaps symptomatic of the developing situation in Nigeria where the arrests of ordinary citizens, journalists, activists and bloggers have become commonplace in the past 3 years. The additional 13% who responded “I don’t know” is also a cause for concern. Their response suggests they are either not aware of the threats to freedom of expression which have developed in the country within the past 2 years; or perhaps, their response is even a tacit admission that they don’t feel completely free to express themselves on social media in Nigeria.

Figure 1: Paradigm Initiative Freedom of Expression Poll 2018

Source: Paradigm Initiative (2018)

Between January 2016 and April 2018, at least 24 citizens, activists, journalists and bloggers have either been arrested or arraigned before courts for comments made online. The legislation which has typically been used to authorize these arrests is the Cybercrime Act of 2015, particularly Section 24. Within the past twelve months however, the government has advanced the Terrorism Amendment Act and Hate Speech (Prohibition) bill as possible new legislative backing for prosecuting freedom of expression in the country. Buoyed by the war against terrorist activity in North East Nigeria and secessionist movements in the South East (which revived ethnic rivalries on social media), although these legislation were developed to tackle these problems, they offer fresh arsenal in the hands of those who want to chill freedom of expression through clauses which potentially could be used to prosecute comments made online.

Another aspect of restrictions to freedom of expression recently observed in Nigeria is the jamming of telecommunications signals around the entourage of Nigeria’s political elite, and mandatory SIM card registrations in Nigeria. The jamming of telecommunications signals around events where Nigeria’s political elite congregate have somewhat become commonplace in Nigeria (Techeconomy, 2017), and the country regrettably is among the many African nations with mandatory SIM registration policies without having a data protection legislation in place.

According to Paradigm Initiative (2018), evidence from Nigeria within the recent past years suggests that while Nigeria has not descended to the repressive depths of countries like Ethiopia and Egypt on digital rights and Internet freedom in Africa, we are not quite far from it, given the range of attacks on digital rights documented in this report. For those who might consider this assertion far-fetched, consider the statements and posturing towards social media by senior government officials, who have become the first in Nigeria’s history to implement website takedowns as observed in October 2017. What they might also pioneer in the near future is also up for guess and a subject of conjecture.

Impact of Twitter Suspension on Freedom of Expression in Nigeria

Nigeria is a party to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), which in Article 19 obligates States to guarantee the right to freedom of expression, encompassing the right to hold opinions without interference, and the freedom to seek, receive, and impart information and ideas of all kinds through any medium regardless of frontiers. Restrictions on speech

and expression guaranteed in Article 19 of the ICCPR are lawful only when they pass a three-part cumulative test:

1. It must be provided by law, which is clear and accessible to everyone (principles of predictability and transparency); and
2. It must pursue one of the purposes set out in article 19(3) of the Covenant: (i) to protect the rights or reputations of others, or (ii) to protect national security or of public order, or of public health or morals (principle of legitimacy); and
3. It must be proven as necessary, and the least restrictive means required to achieve the purported aim (principles of necessity and proportionality).

The Stake of the United Nations Human Right

The UN Human Rights has stated that “any restrictions on the operation of websites, blogs, or any other internet-based electronic or other such information dissemination systems” must comply with Article 19 (Human Rights Committee, 2011). The burden lies on the State to show that a restriction on the freedom of expression passes the aforementioned three-part test.

At the regional level, Article 9 (2) of the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights (ACHPR) also guarantees every person’s right to express and disseminate opinions within the law. The African Commission Declaration of Principles on Freedom of Expression and Access to Information in Africa prohibits States from interfering with the right of individuals to seek, receive and impart information through any means of communication and digital technologies, through measures such as the removal, blocking or filtering of content, unless such interference is justifiable and compatible with international human rights law and standards.

Despite these provisions against any indiscriminate hindrance of freedom of expression, the Nigerian government went ahead to suspend Twitter; a social media platform with huge followership and one of the major news/advertising social media platform in Nigeria. As of the third quarter of 2020, WhatsApp was the most popular social media in Nigeria. The platform was mentioned by 93 percent of internet users aged 16 to 64 years. Facebook and Youtube followed, being used respectively by 86 percent and 82 percent of the individuals with access to the internet. In 2020, the number of social media users in Nigeria reached roughly 28 million (Varrella, 2021).

Leading Social Media Platforms in Nigeria

S/N	Social Media Platforms	Share of Internet Users
1	WhatsApp	93%
2	Facebook	86.2%

3	Youtube	81.6%
4	Instagram	73.1%
5	FB Messenger	67.2%
6	Twitter	61.4%
7	Telegram	56.3%
8	linkedIn	32.8%
9	Tiktok	31.9%
11	Snapchat	31.2%
12	Pinterest	26.8%
13	Skype	12.1%
14	Google Hangouts	11.6%
15	Reddit	9.1%
16	WeChat	5.7%
17	Tumblr	4.1%

Source: Varrella (2021)

Nigerians are avid users of social media. In 2020, Nigerians spent an average of 3 hours and 41 minutes on social media every day. This is significantly higher than the global average of 2 hours 22 minutes. Between January 2020 and January 2021, the number of active social media users in Nigeria increased by 22 per cent, compared with a global average increase of 13 percent. After WhatsApp, Facebook is the most used social media platform in Nigeria, while Twitter ranked 6th among 17 social media platforms being used in Nigeria.

Nigeria currently has 187.9 million mobile connections. This means that 90 per cent of Nigeria's 208 million populations have mobile phones. About 104 million, or just about 50 per cent of Nigerians, are regular internet users. About 33 million (15.8 per cent of Nigerians) are active social media users as of January 2021. About 93 per cent of users accessing the internet do so via their mobile devices. This represents a 22.2 per cent growth from January 2020 – less than a year (Jacob, 2021).

Mobile phone ownership has surpassed ownership rates for radio, television, and computers both at the personal and household levels, and in January 2021, 82.1 per cent of all web traffic in Nigeria was via mobile phones. The largest share of the audience that advertisers reach on social media is young people between 18 and 34. About 19.0 per cent and 14.1 per cent of males and females respectively between 25 and 35 can be reached through social media advert (Jacob, 2021).

How Twitter Suspension Impacted on Freedom of Expression in Nigeria

The ban on the use of Twitter in Nigeria clearly and unduly restricts the freedom of expression of the millions of its users in Nigeria, in contravention of international law for several reasons:

- i. There is no legal basis stated for the suspension of twitter. It appears that the suspension was ordered via executive fiat, which does not satisfy the legality principle of Article 19's three-part test. The Nigerian Government did not state the legal basis for the Press statement to allow individuals appreciate the scope of authority and their options for redress.
- ii. Secondly, the rationale for the Ban fails to meet a legitimate aim under Article 19(3) of the ICCPR. The bald assertion that Twitter is being used to undermine state corporate interests is not one of the enumerated aims for permissible restrictions.
- iii. Thirdly, a blanket ban on twitter constitutes a disproportionate response because it does not sufficiently target the illegitimate speech sought to be proscribed, but instead blocks access to an entire online platform. This contravenes Nigeria's obligations under the ICCPR and ACHPR. As the UN Special Rapporteur on the promotion and protection of freedom of opinion and expression has noted, state actions that restrict or censor content disseminated via internet in a manner that is clearly unnecessary or disproportionate are clearly incompatible with States' obligations under international human rights law.

Given the above clear breaches of the extant laws that provided for and guarantees for the freedom of expression in Nigeria, the study affirms that the suspension of Twitter and thereafter its lifting by the Federal Government of Nigeria constitute hindrance to citizen's to freely express themselves.

Similarly, the paper found that the remote reason behind the suspension of Twitter in Nigeria is the alleged involvement of Twitter CEO in sponsoring the #EndSARS protests in Nigeria. The government had on several occasions after the suspension accused Twitter of

being behind the #EndSARS protests and plan to cause trouble in Nigeria. It is also plausible that the present administration detest for criticism emasculated in the campaign against fake news contributed to the suspension of Twitter by the Federal Government.

Finally, it was discovered that the suspension of Twitter is in clear contravention and disregard of all existing laws by global, regional and even Nigeria itself in protection of the freedom of expression. Taking cognizance of the above, it is permissible to state that the suspension of Twitter which clearly affected millions of its users in Nigeria constitute serious threat to freedom of expression in the country.

CONCLUSION

Freedom of expression is one of the fundamental rights, which are universally recognized and protected. This fundamental right need not be put into jeopardy in democratic country such as Nigeria. It is counterproductive to see custodians of laws become abusers of the law in a democratic society. The blanket suspension of Twitter is an unlawful restriction on freedom of expression and other freedoms exercised online. The government should immediately revoke the directive in line with its international obligations and adopt measures to foster digital freedoms in consultation with all stakeholders.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the avalanche of studies, the paper recommends that the abuse of freedom of expression and other fundamental human rights by public officials should be considered serious that can warrant the vacation of office by the offender in Nigeria. This would help to curtail the flagrant initiation and execution of policies that are inimical to freedom of expression in Nigeria.

More so, the government should channel their energy towards providing good governance rather than seeking to limit the freedom of the people to express themselves through the various platforms available to them. More so, the people need to be oriented on the need to desist from expressing themselves in a manner that constitute obstruction to others in exercising their own freedom of expression.

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